

**IMPROVEMENT OF FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING IN
JOINT VENTURES ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS**

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Annotation: in this article written about the improvement financial accounting and reporting in joint ventures on the basis of international standards

Key words: financial positions, financial statements, resource, company, dividend

Financial accounting - Financial accounting provides various groups of users with information about the financial position, results of operations and changes in the financial position of the company. Its main purpose is to prepare financial statements that show how effectively the company's management manages the resources entrusted to it by the owners.

Financial reporting helps to get answers to such important questions:

— how the company is financed (capital, liabilities), what resources the company controls (assets) (statement of financial position);

— what profit did the attracted funds bring (Profit and Loss Statement);

— what new funds were invested in the company by shareholders, and what funds were paid to shareholders in the form of dividends (Statement of changes in equity).

— what are the receipts/disbursements of funds for various types of activities (Cash Flow Statement).

An investor, for example, will use financial statements and compare the financial performance of several companies to choose one of them for investment.

According to international financial reporting standards (IFRS), financial statements are presented annually, although, according to some national legislation, they may be presented with greater frequency (for example, every six months or quarterly).

Financial statements are considered to comply with International Standards if they meet all the requirements of IFRS.

In order to be able to compare financial indicators, the Council on IFRS seeks to exclude differences in the accounting methods of similar transactions. If some standard still allows two methods, then one of them is defined as the main (benchmark), and the other as allowed alternative treatments.

International Financial Reporting Standards

In 2001, the Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards was reorganized into the Fund of the Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards — FCMSFO (International Accounting Standards Committee Foundation — IASCF). Within the framework of the IASCF on IASB — IASB (International Accounting Standards Board —IASB) was given full responsibility for the work on International Financial Reporting Standards. These standards

became known as "International Financial Reporting Standards" (IFRS).

The activities of the Committee, and then the Council, received international support. Already, many stock exchanges allow foreign issuers to submit financial statements in accordance with International Standards. The European Union (EU)

has approved the requirement to switch to International Standards no later than 2005 for those companies listed on the stock exchanges of EU countries. Many countries are bringing national standards into line with International Ones, and some have adopted them as national ones.

International Financial Reporting Standards

New International Financial Reporting Standards published by The IFRS Council (IASB), called International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The

IFRS Council approved the current International Standards & Financial Reporting (International Accounting Standards (IASs)), published by its predecessor.

Currently, the term 'International Financial Reporting Standards' includes:

— International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs)

published by the IASB;

— Interpretations of the International Financial

Reporting Interpretation Committee (IFRIC Interpretations);

— International Financial Reporting Standards published earlier (IASs);

— previously published Interpretations (SIC Interpretations).

According to IAS 1, financial statements cannot be considered to comply with IFRS if they do not comply with each IFRS and each Interpretation. It should be noted that in accordance with the course program, knowledge of certain national accounting features is not required. When passing the exam on the subject of ACCA 'Financial Accounting', it is necessary

to proceed from the regulatory provisions of International Financial Reporting Standards.

Disclosure of revenue and expenses in the income statement

Detailed preparation of financial position statements and profit and loss statements will be discussed later. At this stage, you will get a general idea.

— The profit and loss statement shows the total business operations of the enterprise for the reporting period, usually for twelve months.

— Revenue from sales in the amount of 942,500 rubles is the total sales (including sales on credit) made during the reporting period. Revenue also includes those sales that have not yet been paid at the reporting date.

— The cost of purchasing goods sold during the year can be calculated: this is the cost of all goods available for sale during the year (i.e. the cost of goods available at the beginning of the year and the cost of purchased goods) minus the

cost of goods remaining unsold at the end of the year. These costs are called the cost of goods sold.

— By subtracting the cost of goods sold from the revenue, we will get a gross profit. Subtracting expenses from gross profit, we get a net profit.

— For convenience, the profit and loss statement is divided into two parts. The first part shows the calculation of gross profit, and the second part shows the calculation of net profit.

— You should pay attention to the article "Wages". It includes only the wage costs of employees. Even if the owner sets a salary for himself at his enterprise, the funds paid for it will still be considered as withdrawals!

Used literatures:

1. The Conceptual Framework is primarily a tool to help IASB develop IFRS based on consistent concepts. It is also a useful document for companies, investors and others involved in financial reporting. IASB, 2018, Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting, project summary. Available at <https://www.ifrs.org/-/media/project/conceptual-framework/fact-sheet-project-summary-and-feedback-statement/conceptual-framework-project-summary.pdf>.

2. For relevant reference materials and reports by the European Financial Reporting Advisory Group, see <https://www.efrag.org/Activities/1606201553344223/EFrag-Research-Project-EquityInstruments---Impairment-and-Recycling> (accessed 16 August 2019).

3. See Financial Reporting Council, 2018, IFRS 15 thematic review: Review of interim disclosures in the first year of application, available at <https://www.frc.org.uk/getattachment/1d8558b8-73bf-4a13-bec7-9c350bfcc1ba/IFRS-15-thematic-report-2-November-2018-v2.pdf>.